

Physical Bases of Heart Acting Case of Women in Democratic Republic of Congo

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ABSTRACT

The hypertension is probably the most important public health problem in our country. It is readily detectable and often leads to lethal complications such as heart failure if left untreated. The present study aims to deal with the physical bases of the heart functioning in order to improve the diagnostic and the treatment of sick persons. In this paper **Kunyima equation**, from compartmental analysis, is proposed and in this equation the volumic cardiac power is dialed and successfully correlated to differential pressure (P_D), factor characterizing the artery state. The cardiac frequency has been found to be the kinetic constant of blood circulation.

Keywords: Kunyima equation, differential pressure, volumic cardiac power, kinetic constant.

INTRODUCTION

The cardiac cycle is marked by the sound phenomena, called noises which are normally audible by simple auscultation. Those noises are the consequence of the alternation of diastolic periods (periods of rest) and of systolic periods (periods of contraction) [1,2,3,4].

The heart, a pump, natural dipole, an engine that is never tired at normal state, can be considered as a natural thermodynamic system filling up functions of a pump assigned to collect the venous blood and to distribute it then, in a continuous way, at the set of the organism after oxygenation in the lungs (alveoli). The right auricle recovers venous blood of the general circulation by means of the vena cava. This blood is ejected in the right ventricle that expels it after contraction in the pulmonary artery before joining the lungs. During the diastole, the left ventricle communicates with the left auricle, the mitral orifice being opened: the blood passes from the auricle to the ventricle, the pressure being lower in this last [5,6,7].

At the end of the diastole, the auricle contracts itself to finish the ventricular replenishment. The pressure of the ventricle blood is then higher than in the auricle and the mitral valves close. During all the diastole, the left ventricle is isolated from the aorta by the efficient closing of sigmoid valves at the origin of this artery. The systole is marked by the expulsion of the blood from the left ventricle to the aorta [8,9,10].

Indeed swiftly beneath the effect of myocardic contraction, the blood pressure in ventricle increases considerably. When it becomes higher than the aorta pressure the blood is ejected out of the ventricle. Sigmoid valves will close only when aortic pressure will become higher than the pressure in the left ventricle. After this shutting intraventricular pressure decreases considerably and when it becomes lower than the one in the left auricle, the mitral orifice opens and the cycle restarts. The left ventricle contains at the end of diastole about 150 ml of blood whose 80 ml only are

ejected during the systole [2,11,12]. Things are the same with the right ventricle.

THEORY

Kunyima equation is deduced from compartmental analysis [13,14] performed through a simple pattern of three compartments such as alimentary canal, general circulation blood and small circulation blood (heart). It consists to imagine the introduction in the alimentary canal of a substance of C concentration (quinine for example).

This material has certainly an influence on blood pressure (P_b) in general circulation and its passage in this milieu (active transfer) is characterized by a kinetic constant (k_1) which is a rate constant determining the kinetic state of the event. Its introduction in the small circulation has a kinetic constant k_2 different from k_1 and modify extensively the energetic contribution [15,16,17,18] of the cardiac system (E). These considerations lead to establish **Kunyima equation**, very prominent and useful, which is the fundamental of this paper as it is hereby shown.

Indeed taking into account the three above mentioned compartments different equations can be written

For this system the following relations can be logically written

$$\begin{cases} \dot{C} = -k_1 C & (1) \\ \dot{P}_b = k_1 C - k_2 P_b & (2) \\ \dot{E} = k_2 P_b & (3) \end{cases} \quad \text{With} \quad \begin{cases} \dot{C} = \frac{dC}{dt} \\ \dot{P}_b = \frac{dP_b}{dt} \\ \dot{E} = \frac{dE}{dt} \end{cases}$$

It can be imagined that at initial time ($t=0$), $C=C_0$, $P_b=P_b^0$ and $E=E_0$. The initial energetic contribution of the heart can be neglected after. When the disturbance effect of k_1 on the state

variables C, P_b, E is pointed out in differentiating the above-mentioned equations by k_1 the following equations can be obtained.

$$(1) \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial t \partial k_1} = -k_1 \frac{\partial C}{\partial k_1} - C$$

$$(2) \frac{\partial^2 P_b}{\partial t \partial k_1} = k_1 \frac{\partial C}{\partial k_1} + C - k_2 \frac{\partial P_b}{\partial k_1}$$

$$(3) \frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial t \partial k_1} = k_2 \frac{\partial P_b}{\partial k_2} \Rightarrow \frac{\partial}{\partial k_1} \frac{\partial E}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial \dot{E}}{\partial k_1} = k_2 \frac{\partial P_b}{\partial k_1}$$

$$(3) \Rightarrow \int \partial \dot{E} = \int k_2 \partial P_b$$

$\dot{E} = k_2 P_b$ (integration constants are neglected).

$$\frac{dE}{dt} = k_2 P_b$$

$$\int dE = \int k_2 P_b dt$$

For k_2 and P_b constants

$$E = k_2 P_b t \Rightarrow \frac{E}{t} = k_2 P_b = P = \text{power}$$

$$P = k_2 P_b$$

The blood flow power in general circulation, neglecting the integration constants, is in first approximation directly proportional to blood pressure (P_b) which is in fact the variation of pressure (active transfer). This equation imposes that the blood power should be reduced to volumic power ($P_V = \frac{P}{V}$) in order to have accurate unit of k_2 . Hence it can be written

$$P_V = k_2 P_b$$

This relation has been called **Kunyima equation** to note the name of Dr. KUNYIMA BADIBANGA, Ordinary Professor at University of Kinshasa in Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) who proposed it. As the cardiac acting is submitted to a cycle of systolic and diastolic periods, **Kunyima equation** in small circulation will be written as follows

$$P_V = k_k P_D$$

Where:

P_D = differential pressure = $P_S - P_d$; P_S = systolic pressure;
 P_d = diastolic pressure; k_k = kinetic constant; P_V = volumic cardiac power

P_b , for a certain age person or a certain age group and in absence of all kind of disturbance (stress, shell shock, presence of foreign substances in blood circulation, and so forth) is practically constant and the present paper takes into account this assertion. In this case effectively it is noteworthy to point out the analogy between **Kunyima equation** in small circulation and the equation in the reference [2,13] giving the cardiac power when 80 ml of blood are ejected in left ventricular contraction beneath the differential pressure.

Note that at each contraction about 80 ml of blood are ejected [11,16]. It is known that affections such as arteriosclerosis, coarctation of aorta, stenosis of kidney artery breed the important increase of P_D . In this case however P_D and P_b are not any more constant, they

depend on time and **Kunyima equation** becomes an homogenous differential equation of the first degree with second term which can be solved as usually

$$\frac{\partial P_b}{\partial t} + k_2 P_b = k_1 C$$

With $C = C_0 e^{-k_1 t}$

$$\text{Homogenous solution} = y_h = P_b = P_b^0 e^{-k_2 t}$$

Particular solution = y_p

$$y_p = P_b = P_b^0 e^{-k_2 t} + \frac{k_1 C_0}{k_2 - k_1} (e^{-k_1 t} - e^{-k_2 t})$$

The corresponding energy is

$$E = \left(\frac{k_1 C_0}{k_2 - k_1} - 2 P_b^0 \right) e^{-k_2 t} - \frac{k_2 C_0}{k_2 - k_1} e^{-k_1 t} + F_0$$

F_0 can be conventionally taken equal to zero.

Also it can be demonstrated that when P_b is constant

$$E = C_0 (1 - e^{-k_1 t}) + E_0$$

$E_0 = 0$ for the same above-mentioned reason. As it can be seen the measure of P_b constant or not allows to determine k_1, k_2 and to get as well qualitative as quantitative important informations of the evolution with time of a substance displacement in blood flow

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study has been performed on one thousand healthy women whose age varies from 20-80 years between November 2014 - August 2015. The sphygmomanometer (Manuel, type **Aneroid 767 Tycos mural de Welch Allyn**) has been used to measure the blood pressure [19,20]. A ad-hoc checking form has been distributed to each woman to collect the data such as blood pressure, cardiac frequency, weight, size, age, sex, temperature, basic food. The observation and calculations [14,21] are our methodology of work. The figures have been made by means of origin 6.1 program.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

The experiments have been carried out upon one thousand healthy women through different ages 20-30 (10/7); 31-40 (11/7); 41-50 (12/8); 51-60 (13/8); 61-70 (14/8); 71-80 (14/7, 15/7). In brackets the blood pressure is indicated. It has been pointed out that P_D varies from 3 cmHg to 8 cmHg. According the each cross-section of life the cardiac frequency (f_c) changes from 60 heart-beats per minute to 100 heart-beats per minute [2,11].

It has been observed that for a given person, P_D and k_k remain constants. On the other side for a group of persons P_D can be constant while the cardiac frequency may present variations between 60-100. So it has been decided to make general tables from $P_D = 3$ cmHg to $P_D = 8$ cmHg giving the calculated values of P_C (cardiac power), P_V (volumic cardiac power), k_k (kinetic constant) for a given differential pressure. The calculations have been completed for the values of cardiac frequencies lower than 60 and past 100. Note however that 60-100 is the interval accepted for normal persons [2,11] and the volumic cardiac powers can be associated to this interval. Also it should be known that heart works continually ten years ago and this is possible with the

proviso that it breeds the minimum of power [10,13,14]. Note that whatever the values of cardiac frequencies in the tables the plots paces remain the same.

Table 1: Calculated parameters for $P_D= 3$ cmHg at each cardiac frequency

f_c (heart-beats /min)	$P_c(W)$	$P_v(W/dm^3)$	$k_k(S^{-1})$
0	0	0	0
5	0,026	0,329	0,083
15	0,079	0,987	0,250
20	0,105	1,316	0,333
25	0,132	1,645	0,417
35	0,184	2,302	0,583
50	0,263	3,289	0,833
55	0,289	3,618	0,917
60	0,316	3,947	1,000
62	0,326	4,079	1,033
64	0,337	4,210	1,067
65	0,342	4,276	1,083
68	0,358	4,473	1,133
70	0,368	4,605	1,167
72	0,379	4,736	1,200
75	0,395	4,934	1,250
78	0,410	5,131	1,300
80	0,421	5,263	1,333
82	0,432	5,394	1,367
84	0,442	5,526	1,400
85	0,447	5,592	1,417
86	0,453	5,657	1,433
87	0,458	5,723	1,450
88	0,463	5,789	1,467
90	0,474	5,921	1,500
91	0,479	5,986	1,517
93	0,489	6,118	1,550
94	0,495	6,184	1,567
95	0,499	6,249	1,583
96	0,505	6,315	1,600
97	0,510	6,381	1,617
98	0,516	6,447	1,633
99	0,521	6,513	1,650
100	0,526	6,578	1,667
101	0,053	6,644	1,683
102	0,537	6,709	1,700
105	0,553	6,907	1,750
110	0,579	7,236	1,833
115	0,605	7,565	1,917
120	0,632	7,894	2,000

Table 2: Calculated parameters for $P_D= 4$ cmHg at each cardiac frequency

f_c (heart-beats/min)	$P_c(W)$	$P_v(W/dm^3)$	$k_k(S^{-1})$
0	0	0	0
5	0,346	0,433	0,082
15	0,105	1,315	0,249
20	0,140	1,753	0,333
25	0,753	2,192	0,416
35	0,243	3,030	0,576
50	0,351	4,386	0,833

55	0,386	4,825	0,917
60	0,421	5,264	1,000
65	0,456	5,702	1,083
70	0,491	6,141	1,167
75	0,526	6,579	1,250
76	0,533	6,667	1,267
78	0,547	6,843	1,300
80	0,561	7,018	1,333
81	0,568	7,106	1,350
82	0,575	7,193	1,367
83	0,582	7,281	1,383
84	0,589	7,369	1,400
85	0,597	7,457	1,417
86	0,604	7,544	1,433
87	0,611	7,632	1,450
88	0,618	7,719	1,467
89	0,625	7,808	1,483
90	0,632	7,895	1,500
91	0,639	7,983	1,517
100	0,702	8,773	1,667
105	0,737	9,211	1,750
110	0,772	9,649	1,833
115	0,807	10,088	1,917
120	0,842	10,527	2,000

Table 3: Calculated parameters for $P_D= 5$ cmHg at each cardiac frequency

f_c (heart-beats/min)	$P_c(W)$	$P_v(W/dm^3)$	$k_k(S^{-1})$
0	0	0	0
5	0,044	0,548	0,083
15	0,132	1,645	0,250
20	0,175	2,193	0,333
25	0,219	2,741	0,417
35	0,307	3,837	0,583
50	0,439	5,482	0,833
53	0,465	5,811	0,883
57	0,499	6,249	0,950
60	0,526	6,578	1,000
62	0,544	6,797	1,033
64	0,561	7,017	1,067
65	0,570	7,126	1,083
68	0,596	7,455	1,133
70	0,614	7,674	1,167
72	0,631	7,894	1,200
75	0,658	8,223	1,250
76	0,667	8,332	1,267
77	0,675	8,442	1,283
79	0,693	8,661	1,317
80	0,702	8,771	1,333
81	0,710	8,880	1,350
82	0,719	8,989	1,367
84	0,737	9,209	1,400
85	0,746	9,319	1,417
86	0,754	9,428	1,433
87	0,763	9,538	1,450
90	0,789	9,867	1,500
91	0,798	9,977	1,517
92	0,807	10,086	1,533

93	0,816	10,196	1,550
96	0,842	10,525	1,600
97	0,851	10,634	1,617
100	0,877	10,963	1,667
101	0,886	11,073	1,683
106	0,929	11,621	1,767
110	0,965	12,059	1,833
113	0,991	12,389	1,883
116	1,017	12,717	1,933
120	1,052	13,156	2,000

Table 4: Calculated parameters for $P_D= 6$ cmHg at each cardiac frequency

f_c (heart-beats/min)	$P_C(W)$	$P_V(W/dm^3)$	$k_k(S^{-1})$
0	0	0	0
5	0,053	0,658	0,083
15	0,158	1,974	0,250
20	0,211	2,631	0,333
25	0,263	3,289	0,417
35	0,368	4,605	0,583
50	0,526	6,578	0,833
52	0,547	6,841	0,867
53	0,558	6,973	0,883
58	0,610	7,631	0,967
60	0,631	7,894	1,000
61	0,642	8,026	1,017
64	0,674	8,420	1,067
65	0,684	8,552	1,083
67	0,705	8,815	1,107
69	0,726	9,078	1,150
70	0,737	9,209	1,167
71	0,747	9,341	1,183
73	0,768	9,604	1,217
75	0,789	9,868	1,250
80	0,842	10,525	1,333
85	0,895	11,183	1,417
86	0,905	11,315	1,433
90	0,947	11,841	1,500
95	0,999	12,499	1,583
99	1,042	13,025	1,650
100	1,053	13,157	1,667
101	1,063	13,288	1,683
105	1,105	13,815	1,750
106	1,116	13,946	1,767
107	1,126	14,078	1,783
110	1,158	14,472	1,833
111	1,168	14,604	1,850
116	1,221	15,262	1,933
120	1,263	15,788	2,000

Table 5: Calculated parameters for $P_D= 7$ cmHg at each cardiac frequency

f_c (heart-beats/min)	$P_C(W)$	$P_V(W/dm^3)$	$k_k(S^{-1})$
0	0	0	0
5	0,061	0,768	0,083
10	0,123	1,535	0,167
15	0,184	2,303	0,250

35	0,429	5,373	0,583
50	0,614	7,675	0,833
55	0,675	8,443	0,917
60	0,737	9,210	1,000
65	0,798	9,978	1,083
70	0,859	10,745	1,167
75	0,921	11,513	1,250
80	0,982	12,280	1,333
85	1,044	13,048	1,417
90	1,105	13,815	1,500
95	1,167	14,583	1,583
100	1,228	15,350	1,667
105	1,289	16,118	1,750
110	1,351	16,885	1,833
115	1,412	17,653	1,917
120	1,474	18,420	2,000

Table 6: Calculated parameters for $P_D= 8$ cmHg at each cardiac frequency

f_c (heart-beats/min)	$P_C(W)$	$P_V(W/dm^3)$	$k_k(S^{-1})$
0	0	0	0
5	0,070	0,877	0,083
10	0,140	1,543	0,167
15	0,211	2,632	0,250
25	0,351	4,386	0,417
35	0,491	6,140	0,583
50	0,702	8,772	0,833
55	0,772	9,649	0,917
60	0,842	10,526	1,000
65	0,912	11,403	1,083
70	0,982	12,280	1,167
75	1,053	13,158	1,250
80	1,123	14,035	1,333
85	1,193	14,912	1,417
90	1,263	15,789	1,500
95	1,333	16,667	1,583
100	1,403	17,543	1,667
105	1,474	18,421	1,750
110	1,544	19,298	1,833
115	1,614	20,175	1,917
120	1,684	21,052	2,000

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to figure 1, the following plots can give wonderful enquiries.

Fig 1a. plot of k_k versus f_c at $P_D = 3$ cmHg

Fig 1b. plot of P_V versus k_k at $P_D = 3$ cmHg

As it can be seen however in fig 1a, the cardiac frequency (f_C) is really the kinetic constant (k_k) and in fig 1b the slope of this plot shows a great dependence of volumic cardiac power (P_V) on cardiac frequency at a given (P_D).

From the **table 2**, the fig 2a and fig 2b can be plotted and they give the same informations. Note that the slopes of fig 2a and fig 2b show the importance of the phenomenon at $P_D = 4$ cmHg.

Fig 2a. plot of k_k versus f_C at $P_D = 4$ cmHg

Fig 2b. plot of P_V versus k_k at $P_D = 4$ cmHg

Table 3 gives rise to figure 3a and fig 3b.

Fig 3a. plot of k_k versus f_C at $P_D = 5$ cmHg

Fig 3b. plot of P_V versus k_k at $P_D = 5$ cmHg

This importance of those figures slopes can be evidenced and ultimately table 4 gives rise to fig 4a and fig 4b with of course the same observations.

Fig 4a. plot of k_k versus f_C at $P_D = 6$ cmHg

Fig 4b. plot of P_V versus k_k at $P_D = 6$ cmHg

The volumic cardiac power P_V can be plotted as a function of differential pressure P_D for a given cardiac frequency

Linear correlations are also obtained but the slope of this plot show in the same way the importance of the dependence of P_V on f_C , more than on P_D .

CONCLUSION

This study aims to give very useful scientific informations to health staff in order to help them to improve the diagnostic and to assure the better medical taking charge of heart failure patients.

It has been hereby demonstrated that $f_C = k_k$. Also **Kunyima equation** ($P_V = k_k P_D$) is now submitted.

Research on thermoexergetic treatment [16,17,21] of cardiac system is continuing in our laboratory and we hope it will reach the goal.

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